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ANALYSIS OF WOMEN'S EMPOWERMENT THROUGH INTERVENTION OF MICRO FINANCE

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ABSTRACT

Women's access to credit is generally believed to result in their economic empowerment. As a result, the provision of microfinance to women has been called for by various international and national organizations in light of their productive role for economic development and women's rights. The impact of microfinance on income has been observed to be variable. It appears that, for the majority of borrowers' income increases are small and even in some cases negative. This is due to the fact that most of the women invest in existing activities with low profit and insecure. In addition, women's choices and ability to increase income is constrained by gender inequalities in access to other resources for investment in household responsibility and lack of mobility.

The access to microfinance, by and large, has a positive economic impact. The impact becomes larger for those closer to the poverty line and it also increases with the duration of membership or intensity of loans as members begin to invest in assets rather than consumption. Microfinance delivery in various parts of the world has improved the economic position of households, enhancing the asset base and diversification in to higher return occupations among members.

The status of the women is connected with their economic position, or status which depends on their participation in economic activities such as ability to access credit, role in decision making in financial matters etc.

Key words: Micro Finance, Women's Empowerment, economic empowerment

INTRODUCTION

This paper deals with the impact of microfinance on the respondents in different dimensions namely economic, social and political empowerment. Women's access to credit is generally believed to result in their economic empowerment. As a result, the provision of microfinance to women has been called for by various international and national organizations in light of their productive role for economic development and women's rights. The impact of microfinance on income has been observed to be variable. It appears that, for the majority of borrowers' income increases are small and even in some cases negative. This is due to the fact that most of the women invest in existing activities with low profit and insecure. In addition, women's choices and ability to increase income is constrained by gender inequalities in access to other resources for investment in household responsibility and lack of mobility.

Hence, the presumption that access to credit automatically leads to women's empowerment is not often true. This is because women with access to credit are usually unable to gain and maintain control of it. In addition

there are additional disadvantages that women face including inability to access information, productive resources and social networks that hinder their access to and control of resources.

The access to microfinance, by and large, has a positive economic impact. The impact becomes larger for those closer to the poverty line and it also increases with the duration of membership or intensity of loans as members begin to invest in assets rather than consumption. Microfinance delivery in various parts of the world has improved the economic position of households, enhancing the asset base and diversification in to higher return occupations among members.

The status of the women is connected with their economic position, or status which depends on their participation in economic activities such as ability to access credit, role in decision making in financial matters etc. The following factors have been used to assess the economic empowerment among the respondents as a result of microfinance.

In order to analyse the significant difference between urban and rural respondents towards the impact of microfinance the following hypothesis has been framed and tested.

Respondents' monthly Income

Respondent were asked their level of income before and after they got micro finance from Commercial banks, the replies received from the respondents are presented and analyzed in table 1 here below.

TABLE – 1: RESPONDENTS' MONTHLY INCOME BEFORE AND AFTER OBTAINING MICRO FINANCE

Level of Monthly Income		Urban			Rural			F Test
		Before	After	Changes	Before	After	Changes	
Upto Rs.2500	Number	55	15	-40	59	32	-27	1.584
	%	36.67	10.00	-26.67	39.33	21.33	-18.00	
Rs.2501- Rs.5000	Number	63	33	-30	82	66	-16	11.561
	%	42.00	22.00	-20.00	54.67	44.00	-10.67	
Rs.5001- Rs.7500	Number	30	96	66	5	32	27	4.420*
	%	20.00	64.00	44.00	3.33	21.33	18.00	
Above Rs.7500	Number	2	6	4	4	20	16	8.811**
	%	1.33	4.00	2.67	2.67	13.33	10.67	
Total	Number	150	150	0	150	150	0	
	%	100.00	100.00	0.00	100.00	100.00	0.00	

Source: Computed from primary data * Significant @ 5 % level, ** Significant @ 1 % level.

It is found from table 1 that number of low income earners have been decreased in both urban and rural areas, likewise the number of high income earners count have been increased in both areas, hence the impact of micro finance has been positively affected in economic condition of the respondents. Before obtaining micro finance 36.67 per cent of urban and 39.33 per cent of rural respondents earns up to Rs. 2,500 per month but 140 after obtaining finance it was reduced to 10 and 21.33 per cent respectively. Income group belongs to monthly Rs. 2,501 to 5,000 has been decreased from 42 per cent to 22 per cent in urban and 54.67 per cent to 44 per cent in rural area. Respondents belongs to income group of monthly Rs. 5,001- Rs. 7,500 have been increased from 20 to 64 per cent in urban and 3.33 to 21.33 per cent in rural. The same increase trend was seen in income group monthly above Rs. 7,500. In order to study the significant difference between urban and rural respondents towards changes in income level before and after obtaining micro finance. It is found that there is a significant difference between urban and rural respondents those who have monthly income of above Rs. 5,000 at 5% and 1%. It is concluded that micro finance have positive impact on respondents' level of monthly income both in urban and rural.

Household assets

This study made an attempt to analyse the economic impact of microfinance on the respondents through household assets hence, the respondents were asked about their level of household assets. The replies received from the respondents are presented and analysed in table 2 here below.

TABLE – 2: RESPONDENTS' HOUSEHOLD ASSETS BEFORE AND AFTER OBTAINING MICRO FINANCE

Value of Assets (Rs.)		Urban			Rural			F Test
		Before	After	Changes	Before	After	Changes	
Upto Rs.25,000	Number	41	8	-33	53	14	-39	20.140**
	%	27.33	5.33	-22.00	35.33	9.33	-26.00	
Rs.25,001- Rs.50,000	Number	63	21	-42	71	29	-42	7.561**
	%	42.00	14.00	-28.00	47.33	19.33	-28.00	
Rs.50001- Rs.75000	Number	32	57	25	18	64	46	10.527**
	%	21.33	38.00	16.67	12.00	42.67	30.67	
Above Rs.75,000	Number	14	64	50	8	43	35	12.342**
	%	9.33	42.67	33.33	5.33	28.67	23.33	
Total	Number	150	150	0	150	150	0	
	%	100	100	0	100	100	0	

Source: Computed from primary data * Significant @ 5 % level, ** Significant @ 1 % level.

It is found from table 2 because of micro finances given by commercial banks the value of assets up to Rs. 25,000 by the respondents both from urban and rural have been decreased by 22 per cent and 26 per cent respectively. There is a significant difference was seen between urban and rural respondents towards changes in holding assets value. The number of respondent having assets value from Rs. 25,001 to 50,000 has been decreased both in urban as well as rural areas by 28 per cent in both areas. It indicate that micro finance have positive impact in assets value holding. Likewise the number of respondent having assets value from Rs. 50,001 to 75,000 have been increased in both areas hence the impact of micro finance has been positively affected in assets position economic of the respondents. Before obtaining micro finance 9.33 per cent of urban 5.33 per cent of rural respondents have assets above Rs. 75,000 but after obtaining finance it was increased to 42.67 and 28.67 per cent respectively. In order to study the significant difference between urban and rural respondents towards changes in value of assets holding before and after obtaining micro finance. It is found that there is a significant difference between urban and rural respondents towards changes in the position of assets holding. It is concluded that micro finance have positive impact on respondents' value of assets holding both from urban and rural.

Family monthly expenditure

Another attempt made to analyse the economic impact of microfinance on the respondents through the money spending for family's monthly expenditure. The respondents were asked about their amount spending for family monthly expenditures. The replies received from the respondents are presented and analysed in the following table 3

TABLE – 3: RESPONDENTS' FAMILY MONTHLY EXPENDITURE BEFORE AND AFTER OBTAINING MICRO FINANCE

Family Monthly Expenditure (Rs.)		Urban			Rural			F Test
		Before	After	Changes	Before	After	Changes	
Upto Rs.1000	Number	74	19	-55	83	21	-62	2.864
	%	49.33	12.67	-36.67	55.33	14.00	-41.33	
Rs.1001- Rs.2000	Number	52	12	-40	44	13	-31	5.672
	%	34.67	8.00	-26.67	29.33	8.67	-20.67	
Rs.2001- Rs.3000	Number	17	84	67	19	91	72	4.271
	%	11.33	56.00	44.67	12.67	60.67	48.00	
Above Rs.3000	Number	7	35	28	4	25	21	7.684
	%	4.67	23.33	18.67	2.67	16.67	14.00	
Total	Number	150	150	0	150	150	0	
	%	100.00	100.00	0.00	100.00	100.00	0.00	

Source: Computed from primary data * Significant @ 5 % level, ** Significant @ 1 % level.

Table 3 shows that the urban respondents spend for family expenses up to Rs.1,000 per month were decreased by 36.67 per cent in urban and by 41.33 per cent in rural area. The number of respondents who spent monthly Rs. 1,001 to 2,000 has decreased by 26.67 per cent and 20.67 per cent respectively in urban and rural area. The number of respondents who spent monthly Rs. 2,001 to 3,000 has increased by 44.67 per cent and 60.67 per cent respectively in urban and rural area. The same increase trend was seen in respondents spend monthly above Rs. 3,000 in both areas. In order to study the significant difference between urban and rural respondents towards changes in spending capacity before and after obtaining micro finance ‘F’ test was applied and it is found that there is a significant difference between urban and rural respondents towards changes in the spending capacity for family expenditure. It is concluded that micro finance have positive impact on respondents’ spending capacity both in urban and rural.

Level of money savings

The respondents have explained that they had a very small amount of money on hand prior to obtain the loan, which they felt ashamed to put it in the bank. In addition, they did not have the time to go to the bank before obtaining micro finance. Hence, respondents were asked their amount spending for family for monthly expenditures. The replies received from the respondents are presented and analysed in table 4.

TABLE – 4: RESPONDENTS’ LEVEL OF MONEY SAVINGS BEFORE AND AFTER OBTAINING MICRO FINANCE

Level of Money Savings		Urban			Rural			F Test
		Before	After	Changes	Before	After	Changes	
Never Saved	Number	127	38	-89	131	29	-102	9.264
	%	84.67	25.33	-59.33	87.33	19.33	-68.00	
Saved with Bank and Other	Number	23	112	89	19	121	102	5.372
	%	15.33	74.67	59.33	12.67	80.67	68.00	
Total	Number	150	150	0	150	150	0	
	%	100.00	100.00	0.00	100.00	100.00	0.00	

Source: Computed from primary data * Significant @ 5 % level,** Significant @ 1 % level.

It is found from the table 4 that a good majority of 74.67 per cent of the urban respondents and 80.67 per cent of the rural respondents explained that they have managed to earn a small amount of money and open savings account in the Micro Finance Institutions after obtaining micro finance from banks while 84.67 per cent of urban and 87.33 per cent of rural respondents do not have savings before obtaining the micro finance. This indicates that the number of respondents who are able to save have increased after obtaining micro finance from Commercial banks. It is found that there is no significant difference between urban and rural respondents towards changes in the saving. It is concluded that micro finance have positive impact on respondents’ saving both from urban and rural.

Housing type

A final attempt made to analyse the economic impact of microfinance on the respondents through the type of the house they have. Hence, respondents were asked about their type of house. The replies received from the respondents are presented and analysed in table 5.

TABLE – 5: RESPONDENTS' HOUSING TYPE BEFORE AND AFTER OBTAINING MICRO FINANCE

Housing Type		Urban			Rural			F Test
		Before	After	Changes	Before	After	Changes	
Hut	Number	26	6	-20	71	30	-41	4.402**
	%	17.33	4.00	-13.33	47.33	20.00	-27.33	
Kutchra	Number	44	12	-32	49	28	-21	12.684*
	%	29.33	8.00	-21.33	32.67	18.67	-14.00	
Semi Pucca (semi tiled)	Number	26	72	46	14	60	46	8.644**
	%	17.33	48.00	30.67	9.33	40.00	30.67	
Pucca (tiled)	Number	4	20	16	6	24	18	5.894**
	%	2.67	13.33	10.67	4.00	16.00	12.00	
Rented	Number	50	40	-10	10	8	-2	2.117
	%	33.33	26.67	-6.67	6.67	5.33	-1.33	
Total	Number	150	150	0	150	150	0	
	%	100	100	0	100	100	0	

Source: Computed from primary data * Significant@5 % level, ** Significant @ 1 % level.

Table 5 reveals that the numbers of urban respondents who are living in Hut and Kutchra have decreased by 13.33 and 21.33 per cent respectively. In case of rural it was 27.33 and 14 per cent respectively. Due to micro finance, respondents from urban who are living in Semi pucca and pucca were increased by 30.67 per cent and 10.67 per cent respectively. On the other hand the number of respondent from rural who are living in semi pucca was increased from 9.33 per cent to 40 per cent and living in pucca was increased from 4 per cent to 16 per cent. There is no major change seen in respondents living in rented house both in urban and rural area. It is found that there is a significant difference between urban and rural respondents towards changes in housing condition. It is concluded that micro finance have positive impact on respondents' housing condition both from urban and rural.

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